

TOXICITY TREATMENT OF CYANOGENIC PLANTS IN RUMINANT: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

This review discusses the harmful effects of cyanogenic plants on ruminant livestock. These plants, including sorghum, cherry, peach, and others, contain cyanogenic glycosides that release toxic hydrogen cyanide (HCN) when broken down in the rumen. Ruminants are especially vulnerable due to the presence of specific enzymes in their digestive system that speed up this process. Cyanide poisoning can cause laboured breathing, muscle tremors, convulsions, and coma, often leading to death within hours if untreated. Diagnosis can be confirmed using tests on rumen contents or plants, such as the picric acid paper test. Postmortem signs include organ congestion and a bitter almond smell in the stomach. Treatment involves intravenous administration of sodium nitrate and sodium thiosulfate. The article emphasizes the importance of early treatment and highlights the difficulty of accessing specific antidotes in veterinary practice. Prevention through proper feed management is essential to avoid livestock losses due to plant poisoning.

KEYWORDS: HCN, Cattle, Convulsions, Coma, Glycosides.

INTRODUCTION

The livestock industry suffers enormous economic losses due to harmful effect of poisonous plants. Grazing, a standard practice in livestock management, exposes animals to a variety of toxic plants, particularly when feed is scarce. One of the toxins that damage cattle the fastest is cyanide, and poisoning usually results from consuming cyanogenic plants. Because of an enzyme found in the rumen microflora that speeds up the hydrolysis of cyanogenic glycosides, ruminants are more prone to poisoning than monogastric animals. The purpose of this review is to investigate the causes of cyanogenic plant poisoning in ruminants and how it is treated.

SOURCES OF POISONING

Sorghum, Sudan grass, corn, lima beans, cherry, apple, peach, apricot, linseeds, flaxes, Marsh arrow grasses, ornamental cherry, almonds, black thorn, and sacred bamboo are among the prevalent cyanogenic plants. Cyanogenic glycosides such as

amygdalin, prunacin, linamarin, lotaustralin, dhurrin, and taxiphyllin are the poisonous principle in cyanogenic plants. These glycosides as such are not toxic but they become toxic when they get hydrolysed in the body (Gracia and Shepherd,2004). The cyanogenic potential of plants varies with species, soil fertility, weather and stage of plant growth.

MECHANISMS OF TOXICITY

In the rumen, hydrogen cyanide is liberated and reacts with met-hemoglobin to generate cyanmethaemoglobin. This combination prevents the last stage of oxidative phosphorylation and deactivates the cytochrome oxidase enzyme. The lack of oxygen utilization leads to the termination of cellular respiration. Histotoxic anoxia is the cause of death in cases of cyanide poisoning in animals. For ruminants, the lethal dose of HCN is roughly 2 mg/kg of body weight. Plants containing over 200 ppm of these glycosides are categorized as toxic.